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Human Being and Happiness: Exploring the Challenges in Its Achievement through Literary Narratives

**Bijender Singh,
Associate Professor,
Department of English,
Indira Gandhi University,
Meerpur (Rewari), Haryana, India.**

Abstract: *Every human being is born happy. However, as one grows, one finds oneself in the sea of sorrows, pain and predicament. It is not the case of individuals but groups, communities and nations to pass through depression and stress owing to violence and other interrelated issues. The happiness curriculum implemented by the Delhi government and the mushrooming of mental health and happiness clinics indicate the prevalence and seriousness of the problem. Against this backdrop, this paper investigates the reasons for societal unhappiness. Who is responsible for unhappiness and human life? How can one live a happy life? The researcher has chosen some literary and spiritual texts to investigate and answer the questions raised. For this analytical research, the psychoanalytical approach will be used as a tool for the analysis of the selected material. The study proves that humans are the genesis of unhappiness in human life. These are human tendencies to heap and hoard more and more physical resources, power and other resources to fulfill the ego and prove oneself to be the most powerful and most prosperous. Nevertheless, no one is happy—poor and rich, powerful and powerless, indigenous or global. Human beings are the main reason for unhappiness in human lives. The more one strands in search of happiness, the more one ends in unhappiness. Happiness is not a social or political phenomenon but a psychological one. One who understands reality may lead a happy life.*

Keywords: Social structures, Human identities, Violence, Self-satisfaction, Spiritual

Introduction

Humans are naturally happy in childhood, so they smile and laugh. One cries only for some physical needs, such as feeding or physical discomfort; otherwise, a child is delighted. However, one gets angry as a child learns language and starts imbibing culture. As one grows older, one has other worries and sometimes even psychological problems. Sometimes unhappiness turns into social evil, and one perpetuates violence. Sometimes, human becomes part of mass violence, such as mob lynching, etc. Thus, unhappiness ends in mass unhappiness owing to different structures such as caste, class, gender, race, ethnicity, colour, etc. Border violence, sectarian violence, homicide, genocide, fratricide, patricide, matricide, etc., occur owing to issues that have no solution. Now, children and students are also in the grip of depression, which sometimes leads to suicide, even due to cyber bullying or sometimes performance pressure.

Objective

This paper aims to investigate the reasons for unhappiness in the lives of individuals, communities, societies and nations. Further, its objective is also to explore the factors, internal or external, for this unhappiness. In addition to it, it tries to find the elixir of happiness, i.e. a way to lead a happy life.

Method and Material

To accomplish this study, literature and accidents in general, spiritual texts, and mythologies will be explored. Psychoanalysis and cultural theories are used as tools to analyse the chosen material. For convenience, the study is divided into three parts: the first part deals with the problems in the life of individuals, society, communities and nations; the second part seeks to find the reasons for all human problems; and the third part

enumerates the challenges and problems in the attainment of happiness in life.

Discussion

The current Problems

Recently, the Delhi govt had implemented the 'Happiness Curriculum' in its schools, which implies severe unhappiness among students. It was quite a playful and worry-free phase in the life of human beings, but this phase is also a dark shadow of unhappiness. Further, suicide by school children after the declaration of results and the coaching centres' students' suicide cases again forces the thinkers that undoubtedly human beings are not happy. Many professionals are either under stress or are on the verge of committing suicide, or sometimes they commit.

The kind and number of cases lying pending in courts again is a testimony to the fact that human beings are pressed between jealousy, hate and violence. There are many instances where we come across the cases of soricide, fratricide, matricide and uxoricide. All this happens at the personal and family level. However, a human being is a social one. Being part of society, one is divided into multiple identities: Black and white, low and high class, low and high caste, man and woman, eastern and western, English and non-English, colonised and coloniser, etc.

In India, people have to deal with multiple structures such as caste, class, gender, ethnicity and religion. If we look into the caste structure, the lower caste people are not only marginalised culturally but also economically, socially and religiously. Consequently, they are exploited, discriminated and oppressed, which makes their lives hell. Urmila Pawar (2008), Bama (2012), Kamble (2009), Valmiki (2003), Limbale (2003), and others depict the pain and predicament in Dalits' lives. Jemeela (2005) and Kaylin (2008) bring forth the hardships and risks in the lives of prostitutes. Sectarian violence is quite visible in partition literature, i.e. Singh (2016) and Sidhwa (1989). Nationalism and violence are

depicted in writing such as *The Shadow Lines* by Ghosh (2005), etc.

The cases of matricide, fratricide, sororicide, and uxoricide are also on the rise. History is full of such horrifying facts. Revenge rape, acid attacks, mob lynching and communal riots in a free nation are also a day-to-day reality. All these inhumane acts of violence underline that human beings are neither happy nor content. All those who are well settled and those who cannot settle well are unhappy. All those saints want to be or are politicians and homely; contrarily, householders want to be saints. Neither the rich nor the poor are happy. So, conclusively, all are unhappy. Sadness prevails everywhere in everyone's life.

Reasons for problems

The reasons for all these inhuman, mindless acts are worldly possessions. Students are unhappy due to the increasing pressure in their lives. The students are assessed by the grades they get in examinations. Grades have become crucial in students' lives, and they must attend multiple coaching sessions after school hours. Consequently, besides the local tutors, the coaching industries have also mushroomed up, i.e. Byju's Classes, Akash and others. In the COVID era, there are more digital coaching centers like weeds. In addition, the entrance exams for medical and engineering studies have become more stressful, leading them to cities like Kota in Rajasthan. Millions of students go to such cities, out of which thousands are unable to cope with the stress and consequently commit suicide. Children are not allowed to grow and think naturally. However, the parents and society treat them like machines, feeding them the data of their aspirations and dreams and expecting the desired outcomes.

Individuals are unhappy because of unemployment or undesired employment. From the beginning, the children are trained and taught the materialistic aspect of life. Money, status, power, and luxury have become centre stage in human life, and a person wants to achieve all this at any cost. Some take courses of

loot and theft, while others use immoral means, which lead them to problems or sometimes to jail. The newspaper generally cites well-educated people involved in robbery and theft. However, they are involved in fulfilling their will for luxurious and fashionable modern life. In some cases, some do not even hesitate to kill their relatives only to get (un)due property share or for inheritance. Tendulkar (1975) depicts human psychology and social reality through the historical character of Tughlaq, who kills his father to become the king.

Besides, rather than postmodernism, modernism has reduced a social being to a self-centric being. Chauvinism has become the guiding principle of life. Postmodernism without a fixed centre is centered on individualism and freedom. Resultantly, every individual has become the centre; thus, the self evades the family and communitarian values, which is why, in some cases, one is unhappy in the existing relationships. One continues to search for a new relationship, which sometimes results in the murder of a partner or any other relatives.

Since human beings are social beings, one cannot survive alone. Loneliness is the greatest threat to human beings, which is why they identify themselves in units: family, community, society, sect and nation, besides language and other identities. This sense of togetherness boosts their morale, resulting in their superiority. Furthermore, it is well-known that no idea or construction occurs in a singularity.

Consequently, society is divided into binaries—ideologically, socially, morally, ethically, politically, economically and otherwise. Therefore, the sense of superiority brings the notion of inferiority too. As a result, men started dominating the others on axes of caste, class, gender, race, ethnicity, etc. All ideas are partial representations of truths. Thus, in an attempt to dominate others, the dominant him/herself is also dominant in equal proportion to that of the dominated. Dominant's problem is that s/he is to keep the status quo and has to face the reaction too, and the dominated one's challenge is the domination and action to overthrow that

domination. Irrespective of ideological practice in vague, all are trapped in unhappiness. So, all ideologies end in unhappiness for all.

The main reason for unhappiness is unnaturalness and an extroverted perception of life. Human beings have forgotten their purpose in life and their authentic self. He has taken the outer or physical self for granted and has been indifferent to his true self, 'the *atman*'. Hindu mythologies are full of the philosophy of life—the true self and its true purpose. 'Know thy self' has been represented only to know the physical self. The true self has become absent from human life.

“Aham Brahmasmi” [I am Brahma] is the core of spirituality, which may lead a person to self-contentment, self-sufficiency, omnipotence, and omnipresence. However, being aloof from this philosophy, he searches for the '*Brahma*' in the materialistic world and its possession. As one gets away from its origin, one becomes impure, impotent and lastly, a non-entity. This is presented in the movie *Ram Teri Ganga Maili* as the character Ganga in the hills is as pure as purity itself, but as she gets down from the hills, she is sold, raped and prostituted. So, home is the only place one can get peace and wholeness. This idea is propagated by Ezekiel (1960) in a poem, “Enterprise”, where it says “Home is where we have to gather grace.”

Besides, the ego is the centre of all unhappiness in modern times. Once a human being becomes selfless materialistically and selfish spiritually, one may be out of all the structures. Once the chains of domination disappear, one enjoys one's true self. When one has nothing to lose, one is the richest; one who is powerless is powerful. As already discussed, all come in binaries, so power in the physical world brings powerlessness, too. Nevertheless, it is diagonally opposite in the spiritual world.

Conclusion

The above discussion indicates that happiness is natural and unhappiness is unnatural. Everything unnatural is man-made. Therefore, unhappiness is also man-made. To bring happiness, one must lead a natural life and listen to the natural self. All worldly knowledge turns human beings into unnatural beings. Therefore, to restore happiness, human beings need spirituality more than anything. Only then can human beings be happy and content.

Moreover, this world is a livable place full of love and peace, human values and dignity. In a nutshell, “Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam” [The world is one family] is the need of the hour rather than the other identities, for this man must lead a life of non-identity. The only solution to restore happiness may be traced back to folk wisdom, if not anywhere else, and that is “*Jai sukh chahvai jeen ko, tai bhondu ban ke rah*” [if you want happiness in life, be ignorant]. Further, it may be said, as Osho says, “Blessed are the Ignorant.” Here, ignorance is used in terms of worldly knowledge. Once one is ignorant, one gets enlightened. Furthermore, enlightenment is the supreme goal of human life.

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